

INTERACTIVE METHODS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the role and importance of interactive methods in the development of students' communicative competences in the higher education system. The study, based on a qualitative approach, highlights the pedagogical potential of interactive teaching strategies in increasing students' active participation, developing critical and analytical thinking, and forming teamwork skills. It is argued that the use of methods such as brainstorming, cluster, Venn diagram, SWOT analysis, role-playing games, and project methods in an interactive learning environment serves to establish effective communication between students, strengthen cooperation, and develop independent thinking. The results of the study show that interactive teaching approaches are an important pedagogical tool in increasing students' social adaptability, communicative activity, and academic success.

Keywords: interactive education, interactive methods, communicative competence, communication skills, higher education, critical thinking, collaborative learning, project method, cluster, Venn diagram, SWOT analysis, pedagogical technologies.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda interfaol usullarning o'rni va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Sifatli yondashuvga asoslangan tadqiqot o'quvchilar faolligini oshirish, tanqidiy va tahliliy fikrlashni rivojlantirish, jamoada ishlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda interfaol o'qitish strategiyasining pedagogik imkoniyatlarini yoritib beradi. Interfaol o'quv muhitida aqliy hujum, klaster, Venn diagrammasi, SWOT tahlili, rolli o'yinlar, loyiha usullari kabi usullardan foydalanish o'quvchilar o'rtasida samarali muloqot o'rnatish, hamkorlikni mustahkamlash, mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirishga xizmat qilishi ta'kidlanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qitishning interfaol yondashuvlari o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy moslashuvi, kommunikativ faolligi va o'quv muvaffaqiyatini oshirishda muhim pedagogik vosita hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: interfaol ta'lim, interfaol usullar, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, kommunikativ ko'nikmalar, oliy ta'lim, tanqidiy fikrlash, hamkorlikda o'qitish, loyiha usuli, klaster, Venn diagrammasi, SWOT tahlili, pedagogik texnologiyalar.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется роль и значение интерактивных методов в развитии коммуникативных компетенций студентов в системе высшего образования. Исследование, основанное на качественном подходе, подчеркивает педагогический потенциал интерактивных стратегий обучения в повышении активного участия студентов, развитии критического и аналитического мышления и формировании навыков командной работы. Утверждается, что использование таких методов, как мозговой штурм, кластеризация, диаграмма Венна, SWOT-анализ, ролевые игры и проектные методы в интерактивной учебной среде способствует установлению эффективной коммуникации между студентами, укреплению сотрудничества и развитию самостоятельного мышления.

Ключевые слова: интерактивное образование, интерактивные методы, коммуникативная компетенция, коммуникативные навыки, высшее образование, критическое мышление, совместное обучение, проектный метод, кластеризация, диаграмма Венна, SWOT-анализ, педагогические технологии.

It is emphasized that interactive teaching methods are important for students of the higher education system, helping them to solve and overcome problems they encounter in real-world situations. A qualitative approach was chosen as the research methodology in this work, as it is consistent with the research objectives. The results of the study show that interactive teaching approaches have a positive effect on increasing active participation among students. Educational resources and communication with peers develop students' critical and analytical thinking skills. In addition, the results of the study show that the introduction of interactive teaching methods can stimulate cooperation among students, allow them to work together to effectively solve problems. Interactive methods also increase student participation, develop their independence and active participation in the learning process. Such an approach also increases students' cognitive development and critical thinking skills.

Interactive teaching, interactive methods are a system of methods based on regular communication, and are a system of teaching and methods with the cooperation and active participation of students. In other words, interactive teaching methods are a special form of organizing cognitive and communicative activities, in which learners are involved in the process of learning, have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons is partly to direct the activities of students to achieve the goals of the lesson. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint work of the teacher and students.

Today, in a number of developed countries, methods that form the basis of extensive experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process are being developed under the name of interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most widespread and widely used in all types of educational institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive educational methods, and there are currently suitable ones for the implementation of almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is possible to distinguish those that are suitable for specific purposes and apply them accordingly. This situation has now created the problem of choosing the right interactive educational methods to achieve specific goals.

This requires rational organization of the lesson process, continuous stimulation of students' interest by the teacher, division of the educational material into small parts, use of methods such as brainstorming, small group work, discussion, problem situations, reference texts, projects, role-playing games to reveal their content, and encouragement of students to independently complete practical exercises[6].

An educational approach aimed at developing communication skills ensures that students actively engage with the educational content, freely express their opinions, and effectively communicate in the process of analyzing and evaluating information (Rahmi, 2019)[7]. This approach is not limited to the acquisition of ready-made knowledge, but also serves to develop communication skills in students by discussing complex issues, exchanging ideas, and finding solutions together. For first-year students in particular, the process of transitioning from being

completely dependent on the teacher to being an independent thinker and active communicator poses certain challenges. This is especially evident among students from disadvantaged backgrounds. Dlamini and Zongli (2020)[3] argue that students' adaptation to the higher education environment depends more on the communicative orientation of the educational environment than on their individual abilities.

The process of adaptation to a higher education institution for first-year students requires them to develop independence, responsibility, and the ability to communicate effectively. This process is mainly determined by the students' internal motivation, the communicative educational environment in the higher education system, and the norms of communication formed in the institution (Alam, 2024).[1] Students' adaptation to a new educational environment depends on various factors, and the creation of supportive pedagogical conditions by the higher education system plays an important role in this process.

This study aims to study the development of communication skills among students of the higher education system, analyzing the potential of interactive educational approaches in the formation of communicative competencies. Defining the concept of communication skills is important, since it includes not only students' speech activity, but also their social activity, readiness for cooperation, and communicative position. According to Lenin (2019)[4], communication skills are related to the process of receiving, processing and transmitting information to others in a specific educational environment and are the basis of communicative activity. Southern (2022)[9] interprets communication as a social process aimed at understanding the logical connection between ideas, expressing beliefs and actions. In this regard, communication skills are an important factor in the academic and personal development of students.

Effective educational models and approaches should be used to develop communication skills in higher education. Such models allow students to discuss information, exchange ideas, participate in debates and work in teams (Rahmi, Alberida & Astuti, 2019)[7]. Educational models focused on information processing, including interactive approaches, serve to increase students' communicative activity. Interactive teaching and learning approaches ensure that students engage in active dialogue during the learning process (Senthamarai, 2018)[8]. These strategies create a conducive pedagogical environment for students to develop their communicative competencies by developing their ability to work collaboratively with peers, express their opinions in a reasoned manner, and communicate effectively[2].

SWOT analysis is a strategic planning method that involves identifying factors of the internal and external environment of an organization and dividing them into four categories:

- Strengths (S),
- Weaknesses (W),
- Opportunities (O),
- Threats (T).

Strengths (S) and weaknesses (W) are factors of the internal environment of the analyzed object (i.e., what the object itself can influence); Opportunities (O) and threats (T) are environmental factors (i.e., those that can affect the object from outside and are not controlled by the object). For example, an enterprise manages its own sales assortment - this is an internal environmental factor, but trade laws are not controlled by the enterprise - this is an external environmental factor [5].

1 picture. SWOT analysis.

Conclusion. The results of the study showed that interactive teaching methods are one of the effective pedagogical tools for the formation of communicative competencies in the process of higher education. Interactive methods ensure the active participation of students in the learning process, directing them to independent thinking, joint problem solving and teamwork. The creation of an interactive learning environment, especially for first-year students, facilitates the process of adaptation to the higher education system and serves to develop a culture of communication. Classes organized through interactive methods strengthen students' critical thinking, social activity and communicative position. Thus, interactive approaches, as an integral part of the modern educational process, serve to increase the effectiveness of education.

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